

**Open Research Case Study
Lancaster University**

**eyetools: A set of tools for eye data
processing, analysis and visualisation in
R**

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This application, for the **Elaine Sykes Open Research Award**, is for a software package I have developed since August 2020. Over the last 5+ years, this package has developed from a collection of ideas and code from my own research work, into a comprehensive published R-package that provides simple-yet-powerful tools for open science eye-tracking data analysis.

Eye-tracking is now an established and widely used tool that provides powerful measurements of human behaviour. Its application across academic research is far-reaching, with major importance to the fields of computer science, economics, psychology, and even having influence on art and design. Eye-tracking provides rich data, offering powerful insights into real-time cognitive processing.

Psychology has taken huge strides over the last 20 years to move research towards open science methods, with the sharing of experimental procedures, open data storage, and reproducible analysis documentation. While eye-tracking is hugely important to psychological research, there has been insufficient work on the development of open, transparent, and reproducible analysis pipelines. The few packages available in R (the dominant analysis software in psychological science) that could meet this need lacked a comprehensive suite of functions and the support for those packages had been largely abandoned. To this end, I developed a new software package in R that would allow users to **achieve the open science aims of a reproducible data analysis pipeline for eye-tracking**.

eyetools (<https://tombeesley.github.io/eyetools/>) provides simple tools that facilitate common steps in the processing and analysis of eye data. The package had two core aims. **Aim 1** was to develop **a suite of functions that worked seamlessly together**. There are now around 20 functions built into the package, that allow the user to develop a pipeline of analysis from the processing of raw data, to the extraction of event related data (i.e., fixations – points where the eye rests; saccades – moments of eye-movement), to summarising those data at the trial level (e.g., time on areas of interest), and generating data visualisations. **Aim 2** was to make this process **extremely user friendly**. To achieve this, I envisaged the package being used by PhD students who had not approached eye-data analysis before. This was important for users in my own lab, but also for the wider reach of the package. To achieve this, I worked hard on documentation, both within the package, and in the [tutorial materials I developed](#).

The **barriers to development** were considerable. I hadn't developed any packages before starting on *eyetools* and so there was a steep learning curve to understand the fundamentals of package development in R. This unfunded work took a considerable amount of time (5 years off-and-on) to complete this first phase. The other major hurdle was **thinking logically and strategically** about the elements of the package, not only from the perspective of my lab's needs, but also how other labs would approach using the package. This meant surveying existing users and realising potential data sources and use cases for the software. I presented the initial ideas and functions of the package at UK conferences and workshops (NW visual cognition group; Experimental Psychology Society) and integrated suggestions into development. I engaged researchers around the world to seek suggestions for processes they would like to see implemented.

In terms of **lessons learnt**, I could have been more mindful of the time needed to write general purpose algorithms that can be adapted for wider use-cases. In this respect, additional time was

spent rewriting earlier algorithms to gain flexibility (somewhat inevitable in software development, perhaps). I would also have conducted even more research on available packages and sought more input from researchers before starting – I'm now of the opinion that it's not possible to do too much initial research and planning on such a project!

Overall, I'm extremely proud of this work. I have now **published the package on the Comprehensive R Archive Network**, the primary source for package installs in R. This makes the package freely available to all researchers across the world (4200+ downloads in 18 months). Meaningful applications have been seen in it gaining citations in two manuscripts outside of my own lab work (one published, one pre-print). I have a *Behavior Research Methods* manuscript in revision which documents the package.